

Ultrasonic accelerated removal and determination of acephate on poly(GMA/DVB) using HPLC method

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Abstract : This study reports ultrasonic accelerated adsorptive removal of an important organophosphate pesticide, acephate using poly(GMA/DVB). Various experimental conditions and their effects on adsorption of acephate have been studied. The equilibrium adsorption data is subjected to various adsorption isotherms (Langmuir, Freundlich, Dubinin-Radjuvic, Flory-Huggins and Temkin). Pseudo-first order, second order and intraparticle diffusion kinetic models are used for kinetic studies. The experimental findings indicate that adsorption of acephate follows Langmuir and pseudo-second order kinetics. Change in thermodynamic parameters is also evaluated. It is found that poly(GMA/DVB) exhibits good adsorption capacity for organophosphorous acephate.

Keywords : Poly(GMA/DVB), acephate, ultrasonic accelerated adsorption, isotherms, kinetic models.

Introduction

Pesticides are frequently used to limit the unwanted and unfriendly insects from agricultural and economic losses. At the same time some problems take birth in the form of environmental damages. Their adverse effects are exponentially increased in the third world countries lacking behind in education, having few and far between sources of masses awareness. The blind, uncontrolled and excessive use of pesticides and the negligence of their proper monitoring and control are acerbating the situation.

Organophosphorous pesticides (OPPs) utilization on massive scale to control crop destroying insects has raised serious environmental concerns including their residues present in soil, water and air. These OPPs have sufficient potential to pollute and cause underground safe water contamination due to leaching down from point sources of these contaminants. The identifiable sources of these pollutants include wastewater from the factories formulating or processing OPPs, the waste containers, accidental leakages during their transportation. It is well documented that these OPPs are toxic to vertebrates including humans. These affect central nervous system¹, reproductive system², respiratory system disorder³ and also cause

genetic mutations⁴.

O,S-Dimethyl acetylphosphoramidothioate (Fig. 1) with common name acephate (AP) belongs to organophosphorous group of pesticides. Acephate is an insecticide which is engaged to handle the sucking and biting effect of insects. Various methods have been employed to remove pollutants from water, one of the most frequently used method is adsorption. Adsorption is a complex process influenced by various forces among the adsorbent, adsorbate, solvent used, concurrently present species in the sample matrix, electrostatic attractions, covalent bonding, hydrogen bonding, non-polar interaction, dipole-dipole, ion-dipole and lateral interactions.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of acephate.

Ultrasonic assisted adsorption is a new, rapidly growing area of research for the removal of chemical pollutants from the environment⁵. Use of ultrasound increases the mass transfer rate by reducing diffusion resistance^{6,7}.

The conventional batch adsorption studies usually require longer contact times for the occupation of all the surface of adsorbent. Potential of ultrasound rapid mixing enables to overcome the obstacles in the way to adsorption.

Polymeric adsorbents⁸ possess unique properties which make them efficient materials for adsorption. Their role in the adsorption of organic pollutants from wastewaters is vastly explored⁹⁻¹³. The polymeric adsorbents by changing the polymerization parameters, can be engineered in terms of their surface areas, porosity and technical properties useful in maximum adsorptions¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

In present study, we report the adsorption properties of poly(GMA/DVB) to remove the acephate from aqueous systems. Poly(GMA/DVB) is synthesized using glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) and divinyl benzene (DVB) monomers. The parameters like adsorbent dosage, acephate concentration, adsorbent particle size, reaction temperature and pH on acephate adsorption on poly(GMA/DVB) have been studied. Materials are characterized by FTIR and EDX. Different adsorption isotherms and kinetic models related with the process are applied. We have used an economic, efficient and convenient ultrasonic accelerated micro-extraction method for acephate. The idea to use ultrasonic assisted rapid mixing is to facilitate the different steps of adsorption that are bulk diffusion, film diffusion, pore diffusion and chemical binding with the adsorbent¹⁷.

Experimental

Reagents and material :

Acetonitrile (ACN, >99.9%), divinylbenzene (DVB, 80%), methanol (>99.9%) were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), α, α' -azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN, 98%) was obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland), glycidyl methacrylate (GMA, 97%) was obtained from Aldrich (Milwaukee, WI). Acephate standard of 97% purity was purchased from Chempure (China). All glassware used was of Pyrex, Germany.

Synthesis of poly(GMA/DVB) :

2.5 mL of divinylbenzene was taken in a round bottom flask, having 120 mL acetonitrile and 62.5 mg AIBN. The mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 4 h, followed by the addition of 5 mL glycidyl methacrylate and 100 mg AIBN and it was stirred at 70 °C for 16 h. Mixture after bringing to room temperature was filtered and washed with

acetonitrile, followed by methanol. The polymer was then dried in vacuum desiccator at room temperature for 4 h¹⁸.

Determination of pH of zero charge (PZC) :

The HPLC grade water (Merck) was boiled for 20 min to eliminate dissolved CO₂, capped and cooled to room temperature. 15 mL of CO₂ free water was added to 0.2 g of polymer, tightened with cap and shaken for 48 h at room temperature. After this period it was opened and its point of zero charge^{19,20} pH was measured with Crison MM40⁺ pH meter.

Acephate standard solutions :

Stock solution of appropriate concentration of acephate was made by adding 1.0 g of acephate in 10 mL of H₂O-ACN (20 : 80) solution, and then volume was made up to 1000 mL with the same solution. Further dilutions were made by diluting the stock solution of acephate.

HPLC analysis :

Acephate residues were determined using HPLC method. The adsorbent was placed in a vial; added small quantity of mobile phase H₂O-ACN (20 : 80). The known amount of acephate was placed in the ultrasonic bath for the pre-determined optimized time interval. After that it was taken out, filtered and immediately injected into HPLC (D-Star Instruments 8424 Quarry Rd., VA 20110-800-DSTAR12), equipped with a Mightysil RP-18, GP 250-4.6 (5 μ m) column and UV-Vis detector, at 215 nm wavelength.

The percent of acephate was calculated using the following eq. (1) :

$$\% \text{ Acephate} = \frac{\text{Area of sample}}{\text{Area of Std.}} \times \frac{\text{Wt. of Std}}{\text{Wt. of Sample}} \times \% \text{ Purity of Std.} \quad (1)$$

Sonication time optimization :

Ultrasonic bath with temperature control was used for the study of sonication effects on the adsorption of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB). Sonication time was optimized with 1.0 mL solution (99.8 mg L⁻¹) of acephate, taken in a vial with fixed amount of adsorbent (0.01 g). The adsorption phenomenon was studied after different sonica-

tion time intervals.

Equilibrium experiments :

The chemical equilibrium was determined using 0.01 g of poly(GMA/DVB), and varying the initial acephate concentration from 25 mg L⁻¹ to 300 mg L⁻¹ with sonication period of 3 min, pH was adjusted at 6.4 and temperature at 293 K and 313 K. The adsorption capacity q_e (mg g⁻¹) was determined using eq. (2).

$$q_e = \frac{(C_o - C_e)V}{m} \quad (2)$$

Kinetic experiments :

Kinetic experiments of acephate adsorption were performed at 293 K and 313 K using the 98 mg L⁻¹ of acephate, 0.01 g of polymer, pH 6.4 and varying sonication times. The acephate at t was determined from the following expression (3).

$$q_t = \frac{(C_o - C_t)V}{m} \quad (3)$$

Results and discussion

Confirmation of poly(GMA/DVB) preparation :

The infrared spectrum was recorded. It shows peaks at 1720 cm⁻¹ and 1646–1650 cm⁻¹ belonging to C=O and C=C and peak of CH and CH₂ at 2800–3000 cm⁻¹. OH peak near 3500 cm⁻¹ represents epoxy ring opening in GMA.

Effect of pH :

The medium pH during the adsorption process has a fundamental role to play. Analyses were performed in the pH range of 1.0–7.0 (Fig. 2) at acephate concentration 100 mg L⁻¹, media dose 0.01 g/mL and sonication time 180 s at 293 K and 313 K. The maximum removal efficiency was approximately 65.14% at 293 K and 62.14% at 313 K respectively at pH 1. The poly(GMA/DVB) particles possess range of binding positions. The acephate loading is due to potential binding positions, the chemical functionalities of acephate and positive charges created because of pH lower than isoelectric point²². The higher basic pH accelerates attack of hydroxyl anions on acephate molecules which lead toward its disintegration, so basic pH was not selected for the adsorption studies.

Scheme of synthesis of poly(GMA/DVB) adopted from Feuerstein *et al.*²¹.

It was observed that at lower acidic pH values, acephate shows better adsorption. This phenomenon is due to changes in solid surface charges and ionization of molecule groups or atoms, changing the mechanism and extent of adsorption²³. The GMA/DVB polymer possesses electron donor groups that can give rise to polar, electrostatic forces, H-bonding at the lower acidic pH values

Fig. 2. pH study.

which can better make H-bridging with the ionized groups of acephate molecules. It may be due to intensive H-bridging at the lower pH 1. It may be considered that at lower acidic pH acephate molecules possessing charged sites could activate attractive interactions on the polymeric adsorbent surface. This adsorption behavior with lower pH is similar to that of porous polymeric adsorbents²⁴. At low acidic pH, the adsorbent surface would be surrounded by the hydronium ions, which may enhance the attractive forces and improve the adsorption on polar adsorbents²⁵. The interaction between adsorbate and adsorbent is a cation-dipole interaction and also van der Waals forces in acidic solution^{26,27}.

Acephate concentration :

Changing concentration of acephate from 25.9 to 399.5 mg L⁻¹, the q_e value increased from 3.00 to 19.50 mg g⁻¹ and the removal lowered from 77.1% to 32.1% at 293 K. While at 313 K the q_e increased from 2.55 to 16.35 mg g⁻¹ and percentage removal decreased from 65.7% to 27.3% (Fig. 3). It is because of the fact that at lower concentration most of the acephate molecules were adsorbed quickly on the vacant surface, while further enhancement of acephate made the media studded²⁸, resulting in slower rate of uptake of acephate inside the polymer pores.

Fig. 3. Effect of acephate concentration.

Sonication time optimization :

It was found that the loading of acephate enhanced with enhancing the sonication period and it achieved a constant point. The adsorption of acephate was initially fast and it became lesser towards the equilibrium point. It is due to the reality that at the initial stages there are more vacant surfaces available for adsorption. The optimum sonication time was found to be 180 s, it is reduced to the greater extent than the conventional reported time (80 min) for acephate adsorption onto granular activated

carbon²⁹.

Equilibria studies :

Chemical equilibrium studies were performed at 293 K and 313 K at pH 6.5, polymer dose 0.01 g, initial concentration of acephate 25–300 mg L⁻¹ with 180 s sonication time and the results are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of the coefficients isotherm parameters for acephate adsorption onto poly(GMA/DVB)

Isotherm model	Temperature (K)	
	293	313
Langmuir :		
q_m (mg/g)	21.339	18.766
K_L (L/g)	0.841	0.465
a_L (L/mg)	0.0394	0.0248
R_L	0.0439	0.0767
R^2	0.997	0.995
Freundlich :		
N	2.3156	2.0171
K_F (mg/g)	1.3948	1.0999
R^2	0.8853	0.9102
Temkin :		
K_T (L/g)	0.524	0.274
B_t (mg/g)	4.15326	3.97132
R^2	0.9575	0.971
Dubinin-Radushkevich :		
X_m (mg/g)	15.889	13.0343
B	1.2E-05	2.3E-05
E (kJ/mol)	201.779	148.278
R^2	0.9605	0.9521
Flory-Huggins model :		
N	2.1418	3.3459
K_{FH}	0.0357	0.0286
R^2	0.8761	0.8978

Adsorption isotherms :

The adsorption isotherms for acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 K and 313 K, pH 6.5, poly(GMA/DVB) dose 0.01 g, sonication time 3.0 min and acephate initial concentration (25–300 mg L⁻¹) (Fig. 4). The adsorption data of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) was analyzed with Freundlich, Langmuir, Temkin, Dubinin-Radushkevich and Flory-Huggins isotherms.

Freundlich isotherm :

The Freundlich model is shown by eq. (3) :

Fig. 4. Adsorption isotherm for acephate on poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

$$\ln q_e = \ln K_F + \frac{1}{n} \ln C_e \quad (3)$$

Fig. 5 shows the Freundlich isotherms where K_F and n were determined from intercept and slopes respectively (Table 1). The n is more than one for the loading of acephate on poly(GMA/DVB) at both temperatures. It means that the adsorption of acephate enhances slowly than the concentration. The constant K_F is linked with the extent of adsorption³⁰. Greater value of K_F for adsorption of acephate at 293 K than that at 313 K proved the mechanism to be more suited at lesser temperature.

Fig. 5. Freundlich isotherm of acephate on poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

Langmuir isotherm :

Langmuir adsorption isotherm is given by eq. (4).

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{K_L} + \alpha_L \frac{C_e}{K_L} \quad (4)$$

Langmuir plot at 293 K and 313 K are shown in Fig. 6.

Poly(GMA/DVB) loading tendency can be determined by the eq. (5)³¹ :

Fig. 6. Langmuir isotherms of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

$$q_m = \frac{K_L}{a_L} \quad (5)$$

The dimensionless factor R_L can be determined using eq. (6) :

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_e} \quad (6)$$

Langmuir parameters q_m , K_L , R_L and a_L are given in Table 1. The factor a_L decreases with increase in temperature, revealing that interactions between poly(GMA/DVB) and acephate are weaker at elevated temperatures. The R_L parameter describes whether the adsorption process is favorable :

- $R_L > 1$ (Unfavorable);
- $R_L = 1$ (Linear);
- $0 < R_L < 1$ (Favorable);
- $R_L = 0$ (Irreversible)

The R_L parameter is less than 1 but greater than 0, confirming the feasible adsorption process. The Freundlich parameter n and K_F (Table 1) are in good agreement with the Langmuir parameter R_L , K_L and indicating the adsorption of acephate is favorable at poly(GMA/DVB) at both temperatures.

Temkin isotherm :

The linearity of this is shown as eq. (7) :

$$q_e = B_t \ln K_T + B_t \ln C_e \quad (7)$$

where $B_t = RT/B$, having a link with adsorption heat. The value of K_T and B_t are obtained from the intercept and slope of the plot of q_e versus $\ln C_e$ respectively (Fig. 7). It is clear from Table 1, that the value of K_T and B_t

Fig. 7. Temkin isotherms of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

decreases by enhancing the temperature, indicating the loading of acephate on poly(GMA/DVB) is exothermic.

Dubinin-Radushkevich (D-R) isotherm :

Fig. 8 shows the Dubinin-Radushkevich (D-R) isotherm³², applied to the adsorption data, used in the linear form as in eq. (8) :

$$\ln q_e = \ln X_m - \beta \epsilon^2 \quad (8)$$

where X_m of poly(GMA/DVB) (mg g^{-1}), is linked to adsorption energy and ϵ is Polanyi adsorption potential³³, the energy needed to elute adsorbed molecule, can be calculated using the following eq. (9) :

$$\epsilon = RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{C_e} \right) \quad (9)$$

Polanyi theory assumed that the adsorption is linked to sorption energy over the condensation energy. The values of β and X_m are listed in Table 1.

The amount of energy E^{34} can be calculated from eq. (10) :

$$E = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-2\beta}} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 8. D-R isotherm of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

The amounts of E are 201.779 and 148.278 kJ mol^{-1} showing ion exchange mechanism³⁵ for the adsorption (Table 1).

Flory-Huggins isotherm :

The Flory-Huggins (F-H) model was selected to measure the extent of surface coverage of the adsorbent. The F-H expression is shown by eq. (11) :

$$\log \frac{Q}{C_i} = \log K_{FH} + n \log (1 - Q) \quad (11)$$

where Q can be calculated by the following eq. (12) :

$$Q = 1 - \frac{C_e}{C_i} \quad (12)$$

While n is the number of adsorbate molecules on the binding positions. The n and K_{FH} constants (Table 1) were determined from the curve $\log Q/C_i$ versus $\log (1 - Q)$, (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. F-H isotherms of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

Kinetic studies :

Pseudo-first order, second order and intraparticle diffusion kinetic models are used for kinetic studies. Adsorption rate is proportional to the driving force and concentration gradient³⁶.

Pseudo-first order model :

The linear form of pseudo-first order model is given by eq. (13).

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (13)$$

The linear plots of $\ln (q_e - q_t)$ versus t yield straight lines (Fig. 10). The values of k_1 (min^{-1}) and q_e (mg g^{-1}) computed from the slope and intercept of the pseudo-first

Fig. 10. Pseudo-first order plot of acephate adsorption onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

order linear plots are depicted in Table 2.

Pseudo-second order model :

The linear form of pseudo-second order model is given by eq. (14)³⁷ :

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (14)$$

where k_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) is the rate constant of pseudo-second order kinetic equation, it can be obtained from the intercept of the linear plot of time versus t/q_t , while the equilibrium adsorption capacity q_e can be calculated from the slope of this linear plot as shown in Fig. 11. The value of K_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) and q_e (mg g^{-1}) are given in the Table 2. According to correlation coefficient values,

Fig. 11. Pseudo-second order plot of acephate adsorption onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

the 2nd order model is more suitable to the adsorption kinetic data than that of the first order model for the acephate on poly(GMA/DVB). Table 2 shows that the value of equilibrium adsorption capacity (q_e) of poly(GMA/DVB) lowers by enhancing the temperature³⁸. The h and $t_{1/2}$ are determined from eqs. (15) and (16), and given in Table 2. There is decreasing trend of h and $t_{1/2}$ with the increase in temperature.

$$h = k_2 q_e^2 \quad (15)$$

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e} \quad (16)$$

Intraparticle diffusion model :

Fick's second law was used to evaluate the data and is given by the eq. (17).

$$q_t = k_{id} t_{1/2} + I \quad (17)$$

The value of I is directly proportional to the boundary layer thickness³⁹. Fig. 12 shows the graph of q_t versus $t_{1/2}$ for the adsorption and the values of I and K_{id} are given in Table 2. According to Ho⁴⁰ it is necessary for q_t versus $t_{1/2}$ graph to go through the origin if the intraparticle diffusion is the rate limiting step. The value of I (Table 2) shows deviation of line from the origin which indicates

Fig. 12. Intraparticle diffusion plot of acephate adsorption onto poly(GMA/DVB) at 293 and 313 K.

Table 2. Comparison of the Lagergren first-order, pseudo-second order and particle diffusion model rate constants for acephate adsorption onto poly(GMA/DVB)

Kinetic model	Temperature (K)	
	293	313
Pseudo-first order :		
q_e (exp.) (mg g^{-1})	12.708	12.192
q_e (cal.) (mg g^{-1})	2.754766891	2.84523229
K_1 (min^{-1})	0.01356181	0.01567866
R^2	0.9871	0.9880
Pseudo-second order :		
q_e (cal.) (mg g^{-1})	14.5871	14.1766
k_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	0.0014	0.0014
h ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	0.3058	0.2865
$t_{1/2}$ (min)	169.1825	165.7298
R^2	0.9976	0.9964
Intraparticle diffusion :		
I (cal.) (mg g^{-1})	4.1389	3.7367
K_{id} ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	0.5079	0.5090
R^2	0.9245	0.9658

Table 3. Thermodynamics constants for acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) 293 and 323 K

Temp. (K)	Adsorbent	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
293	Poly(GMA/DVB)	-0.4218	-22.5902	-0.0757
313	Poly(GMA/DVB)	-1.9926	-22.5902	-0.0703

that surface adsorption and intraparticle diffusion are simultaneously operating during the adsorption of acephate on poly(GMA/DVB).

Thermodynamics study :

The adsorption energies (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) are determined using eqs. (18), (19) and (20), respectively and are given in Table 3 :

$$\Delta G = RT \ln K_L \quad (18)$$

$$\ln \frac{K_2}{K_1} = -\frac{\Delta H}{R \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right)} \quad (19)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (20)$$

K_1 and K_2 are the Langmuir constants at 293 K and 313 K respectively. The negative value of ΔG represents the adsorption process of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) is spontaneous in nature. The negative values of ΔH show the exothermic nature of adsorption process at both temperatures. Variation in enthalpy of chemisorption is in the range of 80–400 kJ mol⁻¹, but for the physisorption is between 20 and 40 kJ mol⁻¹⁴¹. ΔH values for the adsorption of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) are in intermediate of chemisorption and physisorption.

Adsorption mechanism :

Poly(GMA/DVB) is a material which has amphoteric characteristics, so the pH on its surface always changes depending on initial pH of the solution. This is due to the pH_{ZPC} of the adsorbents which has an acidic value, this is favorable for cation adsorption⁴². The sorption of acephate on the adsorbent may be due to the electrostatic attraction between the surface functional groups of the polymer and the cationic acephate molecule (AP^+).

Conclusion

Adsorption of acephate onto poly(GMA/DVB) has been investigated at 293 K and 313 K. It is found that poly(GMA/DVB) shows excellent adsorption capacity for

acephate removal. It has been observed that the adsorption of acephate decreases with the increase in temperature. Adsorption is maximum at pH 1 and it decreases as pH increases. Adsorption of acephate on polymer adsorbent follows Langmuir isothermic model. Reaction kinetics shows that this mechanism follows pseudo-second order kinetics. Reaction is spontaneous and adsorption forces are in between physisorption and chemisorption. Electrostatic forces between adsorbent and cationic acephate molecule (AP^+) may also play some part in the sorption process.

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